

“It rapidly became clear that an incredible number of downloads were taking place, all over the world. The free on demand PDF was the big feature.”

Khan made the switch to open access publishing because he wanted to reach a wider audience. He wanted his books to be read. His previous books had very low circulation figures, less than 100 sales, which is the norm with traditional scholarly publishing.

That changed almost overnight when he published his next book open access. It has been downloaded nearly 16,000 times so far. Citations have also increased.

Khan says it has been the same for the other authors publishing through his open access series. He says it is important that research is disseminated widely and freely, so that it goes beyond academia and the confines of traditional publishing.

“There is a genuine thirst for access to scholarship, a hunger for knowledge which goes beyond academic institutions.”

Geoffrey Khan, Regius Professor of Hebrew at the University of Cambridge and general editor of the open access series Cambridge Semitic Languages and Cultures.

Why Khan believes in publishing open access

Research outputs reach a wider audience within academia

Research goes global

Research extends beyond academia

Research is more influential when people can access it, engage with it and use it

Digital, a cornerstone of open access publishing, drives accessibility